
OW2: Bacterial Cellulose Hydrogel: An Emerging Biomaterial for Chemistry and Life

Saha Nabanita¹

¹ Centre of Polymer Systems, University Institute, Tomas Bata University in Zlin, Trida Tomase Bati 5678, 76001 Zlin, Czech Republic, Email: nabanita@utb.cz

Keywords: Bacterial Cellulose, Biomaterial, Emerging material, Bacterial Cellulose Hydrogel

In current eras, with the development of green chemistry and nanotechnology, bacterial cellulose (BC) has received increased attention not only in academia, and industry but also in day-to-day life especially in the field of healthcare. BC hydrogel is considered a natural hydrogel that inherits the advantages of green chemistry and little toxicity [1]. Besides this, such high-strength fibers of BC provide stronger mechanical properties for materials, making up for the limitations of traditional natural hydrogels such as low strength and poor toughness etc. Pure natural BC hydrogel fiber has good bio-ionic conductivity and light-guiding performance, making it a great application prospect for preparing various emerging materials: in the field of sensors, food packaging, medical devices, wound dressing material, leather substitute material, and so on [2-4]

Figure 1: Visual Image about Production of Bacterial Cellulose/Bacterial Cellulose Hydrogel at CPS, TBU in Zlin.

References

- [1] X. Pan, J. Li, N. Ma et.al., *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 461 (2023) 142062.
- [2] J. Wang, J. Tavakolib, Y. Tang, *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 219 (2019) 63-76.
- [3] H.T. Nguyen, N. Saha et.al., *Cellulose*, 28 (2021), 9335-9353.
- [4] P. Basu, N. Saha, P. Saha, *International Journal of Polymeric Materials and Polymeric Biomaterials*, 68 (2019) 134-144.

Acknowledgement

This work is partially supported by Twinning for Development of World-Class Next Generation Batteries (Twin VECTOR) project Number: 101078935 from December 2022, and is acknowledged with pleasure.

BC is a nano-sized cellulose fibers produced by bacteria that is terminated with abundant hydroxyl groups. The BC producing bacteria are mainly Gram-negative bacteria. The most well-known bacteria is *Komagataeibacter* (formerly named as *Gluconacetobacter xylinus*, a Gram-negative obligate aerobic bacterium that efficiently metabolizes multiple carbon and nitrogen sources to generate BC. The bio-synthesis of BC involves the participation of multiple enzymes and reactions at multiple stages, which can be summarized as **four** steps:

- (1) **Glucose** is converted to glucose-6-phosphate by *phosphorylation of glucokinase*;
- (2) **Glc-6-P** is converted to glucose-1-phosphate by *isomerization of gluconophosphate mutase*;
- (3) **Glc-1-P** is converted to uridine diphosphate glucose by *UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase*;
- (4) **UDP-glucose** polymerized into linear β -(1-4)-glucan chain by *Cellulose synthase* to form **Bacterial Cellulose** [1].

BC is basically a linear polysaccharide composed of thousands of repeating D-glucose connected by β -1, 4-glycosidic bonds. BC possesses a high aspect ratio and a large specific surface area with a diameter in the 10-100 nm range and length reaching several microns.

In this platform, I propose to discuss about a comprehensive review on recent advances of biosynthesis of BC hydrogel and its application including our research achievement on 'Bacterial Cellulose Hydrogel'.